

MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071
Putative protein-
synthesizing GTPase

MtrunA17_Chr1g0200091
Putative protein-
synthesizing GTPase

MtrunA17_Chr1g0200121
Putative protein-
synthesizing GTPase

MtrunA17_Chr4g0005781
**Putative protein-
synthesizing GTPase**

MtrunA17_Chr6g0458091
MtEF1
ELONGATION FACTOR1

MtrunA17_Chr6g0458111
**Putative protein-
synthesizing GTPase**

Supplementary Dataset S28. Nine alternative-source transcripts associated with multiple PRF events. The images represent transcript models that feature the transcript type, length in nucleotides, and relative positions of ORFs (to scale) involved in the production of CPs. Reference ORFs (refORFs) are shown in yellow. Alternative ORFs (altORFs) are shown in pink. The first in-frame start codon (AUG) in each refORF is marked with a green triangle. Transcript models also show the positions and characteristics of PRF events, which are mapped with an asterisk. The description of a PRF event should be interpreted as follows. For example, CP88, -1 (3a2→2a1): a minus 1 frameshift changes the translation from frame 3 to frame 2, which corresponds to the change from altORF2 to altORF1. An altORF1 in this study is defined as the one that starts earlier than an altORF2. Note that three loci in this list, namely MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071, MtrunA17_Chr6g0458091, and MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291, can be regarded as primary sources for some CPs but as alternative sources for other CPs.